

Blended Learning In South African Historically Disadvantaged Universities

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 10, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: September 11, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Blended Learning; Online Learning; Historically Disadvantaged Universities</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8335729</p>	<p><i>The primary purpose of this paper is to evaluate the use of blended learning approach in South African historically disadvantaged institutions of higher education. The majority of South African universities adopted blended learning approach in response to challenges that were faced by students, academics, and institutions of higher education in remote learning approach during and after the period of COVID-19. Blended learning approach became a prominent teaching approach for many institutions and a possible solution for future higher education. However, this approach does not come without its challenges, especially in the context of historically disadvantaged and rural-based universities. This study review literature on the use of blended learning, expresses challenges of blended learning and explores possible long-term solutions for the effective implementation of the blended learning approach in South African higher education institutions. Among the recommendations for the effective adoption of blended learning, the current study proposes collaborations between advanced and historically disadvantaged universities, partnerships between universities and the private sector, technological infrastructure development, increased student support, and training and development of academics.</i></p>

Introduction

Blended learning approach has gained prominence in South African universities due to the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic, which compelled universities to switch to online learning. Blended learning combines traditional face-to-face teaching with online and digital learning methods. This approach offers flexibility and allow students to engage with learning materials at their own pace, while still having access to the guidance and support of their lecturers. The Coronavirus/COVID-19 pandemic was declared a global pandemic (health crisis) in March 2020, presenting numerous unprecedented challenges in the higher education sector which compelled academic institutions to revise their teaching approach and strategy during the emergence of this global health crisis.

Several academic institutions adopted the emergency remote teaching (ERT) approach as an immediate response to this health crisis where there were stringent lockdown regulations imposed to limit the movement and interaction of people to curb the spread of the COVID-19. Hodges et al. (2020) describe ERT as a temporary shift from traditional instructional delivery to an alternative online delivery mode due to emergency or crisis circumstances. This paradigm shift in the South African higher education sector was in line with the recommendation of the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) after consultation with various relevant stakeholders under the theme “save academic year and save lives” as threatened by the COVID-19 pandemic.

As lockdown regulations were relaxed owing to a decline in the number of COVID-19 cases of infections and fatalities, several institutions of higher learning adopted a blended learning approach. The blended teaching and learning approach, also known as the hybrid learning approach refers to a teaching method that integrates technology and digital media with traditional instructor-led classroom learning which allows for more flexibility among students to customise their learning needs and experiences. Several studies such as Zeqiri et al., (2020); Zhang et al., (2020); and Bazelais and Doleck (2018) argue that the right combination of online and traditional delivery represents an effective teaching methodology in institutions of higher education. The blended learning approach became a new phenomenon for several under-resourced institutions of higher learning in South Africa in midst of the COVID-19 pandemic.

This approach to teaching and learning has posed numerous challenges for historically disadvantaged and rural-based universities. These challenges arose precisely because many historically disadvantaged institutions of higher education are characterised by limited resources, rural-based locations and low technology, and poor network and internet connectivity. Over recent years, privileged, or highly resourced institutions of higher education would immediately shift to online teaching and learning due to certain crises in traditional learning

environments which would force universities to shut down such as FeesMustFall students' protests or any violent students' protests endangering the lives of others and to protect university property.

Blended learning approach has facilitated access to education for students who may not have been able to attend traditional face-to-face classes due to geographic, financial, or personal reasons. It has enabled students from rural areas to access quality education and has allowed working professionals to pursue further education while continuing to work. However, there are also challenges to implementing blended learning in South African universities. Some students may not have access to the necessary technology or internet connectivity required for online learning. Lecturers may also need to adapt their teaching methods to effectively deliver online course content.

Several previous studies advocate that blended learning has been working effectively. Krishnamurthy (2020) indicated that the concurrent implementation of contact and online learning has been aided by the universities' ability to develop digital learning methods during the pandemic and provide digital learning contexts, tools, and support systems. Mishra, Gupta, and Shree (2020) also emphasised the need for universities to implement appropriate infrastructure and technological platforms to support eLearning. Many universities have incorporated various technological platforms to support digital learning such as Blackboard, Moodle, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, etc. to conduct effective virtual learning. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the impact of blended learning approach, the challenges associated with blended learning, and possible solutions for the future of higher education in South African historically disadvantaged universities.

2. The Evolution of Blended learning in South African universities.

South African universities have embraced blended learning to increase access to education, particularly for students who are unable to attend in-person classes due to distance or crisis. Online learning platforms such as Moodle, Blackboard, MS Teams, Zoom, etc. are widely used in South African universities, allowing students to access course materials and interact with instructors and other students from anywhere with an internet connection. However, as previously mentioned, implementing blended learning can be challenging for many South African universities. Many students lack access to reliable internet connectivity and computing devices, which can hinder their ability to participate fully in online learning. In addition, some instructors may lack the necessary training and support to effectively teach in a blended learning environment.

To address these challenges, many South African universities provide students with access to computer devices and internet connectivity, as well as offer training and support for students and academics to effectively teach in blended learning. However, this process remains a challenge for historically disadvantaged institutions due to lack of resources and technological infrastructure. The government has also made efforts to increase investment in digital infrastructure to support the expansion of online learning. Despite these challenges, blended teaching and learning is seen as a promising approach to enhancing the quality and accessibility of higher education in South Africa. It has the potential to increase student engagement, improve learning outcomes, and reach a wider audience of learners. Moreover, blended learning is likely to remain a significant component of the higher education landscape in South Africa in many years to come.

3. Review of empirical literature

A proper review of relevant empirical literature would provide a critical understanding of blended learning for appropriate policymaking decisions at institutions for higher education, even beyond COVID-19, for any possible similar unforeseen future crisis in higher education. A study carried out by Zeqiri et al., (2020) investigated the impact of blended learning on students' academic performance and satisfaction at South-East European University. Zeqiri et al., (2020) argue that the new communication technologies provide academic institutions with a new learning environment that fuels and enhances the learning process. The study reported that blended learning increases students' academic performance and satisfaction. According to the findings of the study, student satisfaction with blended learning assists academic institutions in evaluating the effectiveness of using this teaching approach in higher education.

Zhang et. al., (2020) conducted an individualised intervention approach to improve students' academic performance and interactive behaviours in a blended learning environment from teachers' university in China. The study found that personalised learning intervention can effectively improve students' learning behaviours, attitude, motivation, self-efficacy, and subsequently academic performance in a blended learning environment. Both Zeqiri et al., (2020); and Zhang, et al., (2020) suggested that teaching practices that are based on active learning strategies, collaborative work, and feedback sessions have the potential to promote effective students' engagement in meaningful interactions with course materials, peers, and instructors in blended learning.

Bazelais and Doleck (2018) found that the blended learning approach leads to more conceptual change, acquisition of more skills, and higher academic performance in a mechanics course in (CEGEP) pre-university science students. A study conducted by Alducin-Ochoa and Vázquez-Martínez (2016) found that students had more academic success during blended learning compared to traditional teaching for students enrolled in the Materials Science course at the University of Seville. The findings of McLaughlin et al., (2015) suggested that there should be a proper integration of online learning with traditional classroom learning in improving academic performance.

Another study by Kwak, Menezes, and Sherwood (2015) discovered that the impact of blended learning on student performance depends on whether the effect of blended learning is cumulative or non-cumulative. The study found that blended learning has no impact on student performance if learning is non-cumulative and only affects student performance on the quizzes associated with the material covered during blended learning. Whereas cumulative learning affects the performance for the whole course with a strong, negative effect on student performance in statistics for business and economics students at the University of Queensland. The majority of empirical studies under review revealed that blended learning approach presents opportunities for active learning, improved computer skills and effective teaching and learning. Moreover, it is important to stress that different universities may require unique interventions for the government depending on the level of development and availability of resources. For example, historically disadvantaged universities intensive intervention in the form of redirecting funding towards technological infrastructure development, strengthening internet connectivity, training academics, and improving student services support.

4. Complex challenges of blended learning in South African universities

Blended learning in South African universities has posed several challenges, especially in historically disadvantaged universities. Many students lack access to the necessary technology and reliable internet connection, which can create inequalities and hinder their ability to participate fully in blended learning. Black Caucus (2020) revealed that black students lack studying places, sufficient access to electricity and food as well as access to online technologies. Abrams and Szeffler (2020) noted that approximately 5.5 million South Africans live in informal settlements where there are almost four people per household, additionally, only 10.4% of South Africans use the internet at home. Again, South Africa has one of the highest unemployment rates in the world standing at 32.9% (as of 2023) and three people depend on one employed person, which effectively threatens the livelihood of households (Tanga et. al., 2020).

The education system in South Africa remains complex, with historical inequalities inherited from the apartheid regime. A majority of South African students come from underprivileged backgrounds studying in historically disadvantaged and rural-based universities such as the University of Zululand, University of Venda, University of Limpopo, University of Fort Hare, University of Western Cape, and Walter Sisulu University. These general yet crucial socio-economic factors are critical impediments to the effective implementation of blended learning in South African universities which need to be considered before blended learning can be adopted successfully.

5. Challenges faced by students in a blended learning environment

5.1 Technological infrastructure and connectivity

Many universities in South Africa face challenges with infrastructure and connectivity, particularly in rural areas. This can make it difficult for students to access online resources and participate in online activities. The quality of internet connectivity and power supply in many rural areas of South Africa is poor, making it difficult for students to successfully participate in online learning. Many students in South Africa come from disadvantaged backgrounds and may not have access to the necessary technology, such as computers and reliable internet, needed for online learning. It is important to stress that not all students have access to the technology needed to participate in blended learning such as computers, laptops, data bundles, and reliable internet connectivity. This can make it difficult for them to navigate the online environment and effectively engage with course content. These issues can disrupt their learning experience and cause frustration during the process of learning and assessments. Moreover, not all students are adequately trained on how to use the technology and online platforms necessary for blended learning. This has created a steep learning curve for students, as some students may not be able to grasp content effectively.

5.2 Limited engagement and interaction

Blended learning reduces the amount of direct interaction between students and teachers. Some students may struggle with the absence of in-person communication, which can hinder their ability to seek clarification, or engage in collaborative activities. Some students may struggle with the online components, such as understanding complex concepts without direct teacher guidance or adapting to different modes of instruction. Blended learning reduces opportunities for social interaction among peers. Students may miss out on building relationships, participating in group discussions, and engaging in extracurricular activities. Due to the nature of online and in-person instruction, teachers may have limited availability for one-on-one support or may not be able to provide timeous feedback, leading to delayed responses to student inquiries.

5.3 Self-motivation and time management

Blended learning requires students to be self-disciplined and manage their time effectively. They need to stay motivated, complete online assignments, and attend virtual classes while balancing other responsibilities. Some students may find it challenging to maintain focus and stay organised without the physical structure of a traditional classroom. Blended learning requires students to take more responsibility for their learning. They need to stay motivated and self-disciplined to complete online modules, watch lectures, or engage in virtual discussions. A lack of motivation and self-discipline can lead to procrastination and even failing the course.

5.4 Mental health

Blended learning can sometimes result in an increased workload as students need to manage both online assignments and in-person activities. They may find it difficult to strike a balance, leading to stress, anxiety, overwhelm, and depression as they study in isolation which may adversely affect the mental health of students.

5.5 Socio-economic disparities

Blended learning relies heavily on internet access and digital resources. Students from disadvantaged backgrounds may not have reliable internet access or the necessary devices to participate effectively. This digital divide can create inequities in access to education and hinder some students' ability to engage effectively in blended learning.

6. Blended learning challenges faced by academics

6.1 Technological difficulties

Blended learning heavily relies on technology, and academics may encounter technical issues such as internet connectivity problems, software glitches, or compatibility issues with different devices. These technological challenges can disrupt the flow of the class and impede effective teaching and learning in a blended learning environment.

6.2 Maintaining student engagement and interaction

Academics need to find ways to keep students actively participating and motivated, especially during online activities or discussions. They may have to employ various online tools, interactive content, or collaborative activities to maintain student engagement. Academics may need to find innovative strategies to keep students engaged, such as using interactive online discussions, multimedia resources, and promote collaborative projects to allow for student's engagement and cooperation.

6.3 Training and professional development

Academics may require training and professional development to effectively navigate the complexities of blended learning. Learning new technologies, instructional design strategies, and online pedagogies can be time-consuming but necessary for successful implementation. Many academics may not have the necessary skills or training to effectively use online tools and technologies, which can impact the quality of the curriculum. Instructors may need training and support to effectively integrate online and face-to-face learning activities. They need to develop digital literacy skills, learn new pedagogical approaches, and familiarise themselves with various advanced educational technologies. Institutions of higher education have the responsibility to provide adequate resources, workshops, and ongoing support to help academics adapt to the blended learning environment (Mtshali & Mtshali, 2020; Dzotsi et al., 2021).

6.4 Socio-economic disparities

Blended learning can introduce disparities in access to technology and internet connectivity, which can affect students' ability to fully participate in the learning process. Academics need to consider the diverse needs of their students and ensure that they have equal opportunities to access and engage with course materials. This may involve providing alternative resources, accommodating different learning styles, and addressing any accessibility concerns. Universities have the responsibility to address the digital divide and provide support to students who face barriers to accessing online platforms using media and technology (Makoe et al., 2019; Hodges et al., 2020).

6.5 Assessment and evaluation methods

Designing effective assessments in a blended learning format can be challenging. Academics need to develop assessment methods that evaluate students' learning outcomes accurately while considering the limitations and opportunities presented by online and in-person components. Academics may need to explore alternative assessment formats, such as online quizzes, collaborative projects, or presentations, and ensure integrity in remote assessments. Online assessments can pose challenges for ensuring academic integrity and quality assurance, such as preventing cheating, maintaining consistency, and providing timely feedback. Instructors need to ensure that assessment methods are appropriate for both online and face-to-face learning activities and that they accurately measure student learning outcomes.

7. Blended learning challenges in historically disadvantaged universities

Historically disadvantaged universities face various key challenges when implementing blended learning due to a variety of factors such as limited resources, infrastructure constraints, and students' socio-economic backgrounds. These challenges can further exacerbate the existing inequalities and hinder the educational experience for students from disadvantaged background. Most first-year entering students (FTENs), for example, at the University of Zululand (UNIZULU), come from rural areas where they are not exposed to the use of computers. Many students were given laptops by universities, including the University of Zululand, a historically disadvantaged institution, however, this had its own challenges. Despite UNIZULU's extensive efforts to promote online learning, network connection remains an issue due to the diverse geographical areas from which most students reside. This demonstrates that UNIZULU faces infrastructural challenges like other South African historically disadvantaged universities.

Corrado (2020) stressed that lockdown regulations further disadvantaged students from marginalised societies where students reside in deeply rural areas and overcrowded households with several responsibilities that hinder their studies at home. Tadesse and Muluye (2020) noted that there is inequality among urban and rural students, students from low-income or high-income, and literate or illiterate parents. Hence, students from illiterate and low-income households often struggle to keep up with online learning.

7.1 Socio-economic disparities

Socio-economic disparities prevail when students from disadvantaged backgrounds may not have access to reliable internet connections, computers, or other necessary devices. This lack of access to technology can hinder their ability to participate fully in online learning activities and access course materials. Historically disadvantaged universities may have students who are less familiar with using technology for academic purposes. Students from historically disadvantaged institutions who lack technological literacy may struggle to adapt to this new mode of instruction. Rural-based universities may have a higher prevalence of students who lack access to personal computers, laptops, or other necessary digital devices. This digital divide can create inequalities in accessing online materials, submitting assessments, and participating in virtual discussions, thus putting rural-based learners in a disadvantaged position (Baturay and Mtebe, 2020).

7.2 Limited infrastructure and resources

Historically disadvantaged institutions may lack necessary technological infrastructure and resources to support blended learning effectively, including reliable internet connectivity, computer labs, software licenses, learning management systems, and technical support (Dhir, 2021). Insufficient network infrastructure and low bandwidth in rural areas can lead to slow or unreliable internet access, making it difficult for students and faculty to participate in virtual meetings, and engage in collaborative activities. Historically disadvantaged universities often have limited resources compared to well-established institutions to allow for effective blended learning environment.

Rural-based universities often have limited financial resources, making it challenging to invest in the necessary infrastructure, software, and technical support required for a successful blended learning environment. Securing funding by historically disadvantaged universities can be challenging, potentially hindering the implementation and sustainability of blended learning initiatives. To overcome connectivity challenges, the government has launched initiatives to enhance internet connectivity and bandwidth in historically disadvantaged universities. For example, the Department of Science and Innovation (2021) reported that the South African National Research and Education Network (SANReN) has implemented the South African National Research and Education Network (SA NREN) Extension Programme, which aims to improve internet connectivity in all universities and science councils (Department of Science and Innovation, 2021).

7.3 Technological skills and literacy

Blended teaching and learning require a certain level of technological proficiency, including computer literacy and digital skills. Students from disadvantaged backgrounds may not have prior exposure to technology or may not be familiar with online learning platforms. This can make it difficult for them to navigate virtual classrooms, access online resources, and engage in collaborative online activities. Academics in rural-based universities such as the University of Zululand may face challenges in adapting to new technologies and learning management systems. Universities may need to provide training workshops to equip academics with relevant technical skills to successfully facilitate blended learning environment (Mtshali & Mtshali, 2020; and Dzotsi et al., 2021).

7.4 Equity and inclusion

Blended learning needs to be implemented in a manner that ensures equity and inclusion for all students. Historically disadvantaged universities must consider the diverse needs of their student population, including those with disabilities, language barriers, and cultural differences (Hodges et al., 2020). Providing accessible and inclusive online learning experiences can be a challenge without the necessary resources. Many students at historically disadvantaged universities come from poor backgrounds. They may lack access to personal computers, reliable internet, or other necessary technology devices. This digital divide can impede their ability to effectively participate in blended learning, leading to unequal educational challenges and opportunities among students.

7.5 Assessment and evaluation

Assessing student learning and providing feedback in a blended learning environment can be complex. Historically disadvantaged universities may face challenges in developing effective assessment strategies that align with online instruction. Ensuring fairness, reliability, and validity in the assessment process can be particularly challenging when students are not physically present. To address these challenges, historically disadvantaged universities can focus on improving infrastructure and technology access, providing training for academics and students, and implementing inclusive practices.

8. Government Response in Historically Disadvantaged Universities

To address some of the key challenges faced by historically disadvantaged universities, governments can implement various mechanisms to support low-resourced universities, including providing financial assistance, training, and infrastructure development.

8.1 Provision of funding and grants

Governments can provide additional funding and grants specifically targeted at low-resourced universities to enhance their technological infrastructure, purchase necessary equipment such as laptops, tablets, and cameras, and improve internet connectivity, and provide training in online teaching methods. These funds can help universities to strengthen their online learning capabilities and reduce the digital divide among students. Governments may also consider providing grants or subsidies to help students from disadvantaged backgrounds access necessary technology or internet connectivity. To ensure that students have access to the necessary technology for blended learning, the government has implemented various initiatives. For example, the DHET's University Capacity Development Programme (UCDP) provides funding to universities for the procurement of digital resources and devices (DHET, 2020). Additionally, the National Student Financial Aid Scheme (NSFAS) has included provisions for providing laptops or tablets to students who qualify for financial assistance (DHET, 2020).

8.2 Infrastructure development

Governments can invest in improving infrastructure of low-resourced universities, including upgrading computer labs, creating virtual learning environments, and setting up video conferencing facilities. These measures aimed to enhance the quality of blended learning and ensure students and teachers have access to the necessary resources required for the blended learning environment. The Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) reported to have initiated several projects to improve internet connectivity and provide necessary infrastructure such as computer labs and Wi-Fi access points in historically disadvantaged universities (DHET, 2020).

8.3 Training and capacity building

Governments can organise training programmes and workshops for academic staff to develop their skills in delivering effective blended learning. These initiatives should focus on building educators' capacity to design online courses, facilitate virtual discussions, and effectively utilise learning management systems and other online tools. Historically disadvantaged universities face challenges in terms of faculty preparedness for blended learning. The government has responded by providing training and support to universities. For, example, DHET offers capacity-building programs and workshops to enhance teaching and learning practices in digital environments (DHET, 2020). The DHET also provide funding initiatives like the University Capacity Development Programme to support the development of high-quality blended learning curricula (DHET, 2020).

Governments can also encourage low-resourced universities to establish partnerships with other well-established institutions, both domestically and internationally, to share resources, knowledge, and best practices in blended learning. These partnerships can provide access to expertise, resources, and shared knowledge in blended learning practices. Collaboration with private sector entities, such as technology companies, can also help universities acquire necessary equipment and software at reduced costs or through donations.

Governments can offer incentives to encourage these partnerships, such as tax benefits or recognition for corporate social responsibility initiatives. As previously mentioned, the DHET, in collaboration with universities, has developed various initiatives such as the University Capacity Development Programme (UCDP) to provide training and support for lecturers in historically disadvantaged universities. The South African Institute for Distance Education (SAIDE), in collaboration with the DHET, has also initiated projects such as the South African Open Textbook System (OTRS) to provide free, high-quality educational resources to students and educators (DHET, 2020).

8.4 Research and Development Initiatives

Governments can promote research and development initiatives to explore innovative approaches to blended learning specifically tailored to the needs of low-resourced universities. This may include solutions for low-bandwidth or low-cost technology alternatives to support online learning. Governments can invest in research initiatives to understand the specific challenges faced by low-resourced universities during blended learning and develop evidence-based policies and strategies. Research outcomes can inform the development of targeted support programmes and interventions. Governments can also create platforms for knowledge sharing and best practice exchange among universities to foster collaboration and learning from successful blended learning experiences. The government has emphasised the importance of collaboration and knowledge sharing among universities to address blended learning challenges. These initiatives include the South African Institute for Distance Education (SAIDE) and South African Higher Education Blended Learning (SAHEBL) Communities of Practice facilitate networking and collaboration among institutions (DHET, 2020).

8.5 Student support services

Governments can expand student support services to ensure that learners from low-income backgrounds have access to necessary resources. This can involve expanding financial aid programmes, bursaries, and scholarships to support students who may face increased financial challenges due to the transition to blended learning. Additionally, governments can collaborate with universities to provide mental health services, counselling, and academic support resources to help students navigate unique challenges of blended learning, especially for students from previously disadvantaged backgrounds. The government has recognised the importance of student

support services in facilitating successful blended learning experiences. The DHET has established the National Institute for Higher Education Support (NIHES) to provide financial and academic support services to historically disadvantaged university students, including those who study through blended learning (DHET, 2020).

8.6 Monitoring and Evaluation

Governments can establish mechanisms to monitor the progress and effectiveness of blended learning initiatives in low-resourced universities. This allows for continuous evaluation and improvement of strategies and interventions to ensure the desired learning outcomes are achieved during blended learning. Monitoring and evaluation can involve regular evaluations of online courses, feedback collection from students and academics, and measuring learning outcomes. The data collected from evaluations ought to inform future policy decisions and allow for continuous improvement in the quality of blended learning programmes. A comprehensive government response to the challenges faced by low-resourced universities during blended learning requires a multi-faceted approach, addressing financial, infrastructural, training, regulatory, and research aspects. By providing necessary support, governments can ensure that all universities adapt to the demands of blended learning and provide quality education.

9. Concluding Remarks

The COVID-19 crisis revealed numerous institutional inequalities across South African universities which continue to present several challenges for historically disadvantaged universities to be in a better position for blended learning in the foreseeable future. It is imperative to note that historically disadvantaged institutions of higher learning remain behind compared to privileged highly resourced universities in terms of infrastructure, technology, and resources in general, which would enable blended learning approach to be implemented and function effectively for historically disadvantaged universities. Notwithstanding exceptional government's effort to ensure effective blended learning in higher education, it is noteworthy to stress that historically disadvantaged universities still require special support and intervention from the government. It is also important to understand the learning barriers that students face during blended learning so that the higher education sector can be more inclusive and meet student needs in the future.

Furthermore, the study recommend that academics must be properly trained and equipped with necessary skills to facilitate blended learning environment, and first-year entering students (FTENS) must also be trained on the appropriate use of online learning technologies. Importantly, there must be necessary support in place to assist students from poor family backgrounds such as procurement of laptops and data bundles, and basic computer training to ensure effective blended learning for many students from previously disadvantaged universities. Moreover, it is imperative to emphasise that there must be necessary monitoring and evaluation mechanisms to ensure the effective implementation of the blended learning in South African historically disadvantaged universities. Blended learning as a recommended future teaching approach in higher education provides a great balance of face-to-face learning activities integrated with opportunities to engage in the online learning environment.

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